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Second reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans

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Deliverable 7.2

Deliverable

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Abbreviation list

GA (Grant Agreement)

HEI (Higher Education Institution)

KER (Key Exploitable Result)

ML (Milestone)

WP (Work Package)

WPL (Work Package Leader)

Document Updates

This revised version of the deliverable incorporates the feedback from the European Commission, addressing the following inquiries:

- 1) The document provides a good overview of the dissemination activities performed during the period under review. Proper statistics are provided for the social media demonstrating an arising interest in the project activities. Particularly impressive is the list of the alliances and Universities currently involved in the aUPaEU Agora but it is not specified the level and typology of involvement.
- 2) In-person events are listed lacking an analysis of the impact generated (number of attendees, target audience, contacts generated and follow up actions).

The document now explicitly addresses these comments. Specifically, the document has been revised as follows:

1) As suggested by the reviewer, and as discussed during the review meeting, Section 2.1.2.1. “Definition of Audiences” and the two tables in the Appendix (Appendix A and Appendix B) have been revised to provide a clearer definition of terms and a more detailed reference to the typology of involvement of alliances and Universities listed in the aUPaEU Agora network. Specifically, the terminology has been refined to clarify that, as a result of stakeholder mapping activities, the aUPaEU Agora network includes the contacts of 613 individual stakeholders from 48 alliances and 142 Universities across 23 countries. Within this broad network of stakeholders listed in the aUPaEU Agora, a sub-group of 15 Alliances has been identified as potential Allies. In line with the aUPaEU communication strategy, which adopts a layered approach to progressively expanding engagement, the level and typology of involvement vary across target groups, and evolve dynamically over time, with particular reference to the identification and targeting of Alliances throughout the project’s execution. Details of this differentiation are provided in Section 2.1.2.1 (pp. 10–11).

2) Section 2.2.6.2 “Externally Organized Events” has been revised to address the reviewer’s comment. In particular, Table 4 has been added to provide a visual overview of aUPaEU’s participation in externally organized events. This is complemented by a description of the impact generated, including the number of attendees, target audiences, contacts established, and follow-up actions undertaken. Please refer to Table 4 (p. 29) and the revised text (pp. 31–33).

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1. Introduction

1.1 aUPaEU Project and Mission

The aUPaEU (A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities) project was launched in January 2023 and will end in December 2027. It has received 3.4 million funding from the European Commission in the framework of the [European Research Area call \(HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01\)](#) for the integration and implementation of acceleration services.

aUPaEU is based on the collaboration of two European Alliances under the European Universities Initiative, [Unite!](#) and [EPiCUR](#). Five Universities are involved in the project, spanning from eastern to western Europe: on the side of Unite!: [Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya](#), also including [IThinkUPC](#), [Grenoble INP - UGA](#) and [Politecnico di Torino](#); for EPiCUR, [Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu](#) and [Karlsruher Institut für Technologie \(KIT\)](#).

aUPaEU's mission is to provide tangible digital services to accelerate the transformation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The project's focus is the integration and implementation of acceleration services for the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions.

By developing a digital platform, "Agora", aUPaEU provides tangible acceleration services towards HEI transformation, focusing on six major areas of the HEI transformation agenda: capacity, infrastructure, and resource sharing; researcher career attractiveness; collaboration with R&I ecosystem actors; open science; societal outreach; and gender equality.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

This document, D7.2, Second Reporting on Communication and Dissemination Plans, is an update of the first Work Package 7 Deliverable: D7.1 *First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholder mapping*. D7.2 provides an overview of the activities carried out in the project, ongoing activities and updates on the planned activities until December 31, 2027 (M60), the end of the project.

2. Updated Communication and Dissemination Plans

2.1.1 Objectives

aUPaEU's key communication and dissemination objectives are to:

- Create a coherent and meaningful narrative to explain acceleration services and Agora
- Valorise project results and outcomes
- Engage with stakeholders
- Exploit the project's outcomes

The dissemination and communication strategy paves the way for the adoption of the methodology and findings of the project by university Alliances and Higher Education Institutions across Europe.

WP7 is dedicated to the dissemination of results, as well as the consolidation and maintenance of contact with relevant project stakeholders, promoting their involvement in the progress of the project.

In particular, WP7 aims to create a coherent and meaningful narrative that will explain the reach and depth of the acceleration services being developed inside the digital platform called "Agora" and ultimately promote the adoption and use of Agoras.

2.1.2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

aUPaEU's WPs represent the primary source of information on project outcomes (WP1 coordination and policy, WP2 needs analysis, WP3 data analysis, WP4 business processes and policy, WP5 digital services development, and WP6 testing). Work Package 7 is a transversal WP that captures the relevant results from each WP to produce and disseminate information, both on individual WP progress and on overall outcomes.

The communication and dissemination activities follow a strategy specifically designed around the different phases of services' development: from creation or co-creation to deployment and implementation. This strategy is centred on the definition of different audiences, which are our targets for the dissemination and communication of information. In what follows, the processes for defining audiences and the stages of acceleration development are described in detail.

2.1.2.1 Definition of Audiences

The communication and dissemination strategy requires the definition of target audiences. We first identified different categories of stakeholders in the stakeholder map (D7.1 First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping). Stakeholders were then structured into macro-categories: core stakeholders (universities belonging to the European Alliances Unite! and EPICUR, and that are either direct or indirect beneficiaries of the aUPaEU project); extended stakeholders, (Citizens, HEIs and research institutions, University Alliances, HEIs and research institutions networks, Public administration, and Industry and businesses that are non-core stakeholders).

The aUPaEU communication strategy has been designed to support a progressive expansion of communication activities. It started with core stakeholders - Alliances already actively participating in the project (Unite! and Epicur) - and is gradually extending to other stakeholders (extended stakeholders), in particular the two sister projects¹ and other Alliances.

To facilitate this process, the category of extended stakeholders has been further segmented, identifying Allies as the first target audience. Allies are any stakeholders (Alliances and consortia of universities) who have already expressed an interest in receiving a tailored Agora and in co-creating with us its acceleration services. Once actively involved in the design of services and the Agora, Allies transition into core aUPaEU stakeholders.

As such, Allies represent the immediate target of communication and dissemination activities in the year(s) to come. This approach progressively broadens the target audience of communication strategies, expanding from core stakeholders to extended stakeholders. Specifically, it extends outreach from Unite! and Epicur to the Allies, including the two sister projects, while gradually involving additional partners in the development of acceleration services and potential new Agora(s). Particular attention will be given to Widening areas, engaging them either as co-creators or users of new acceleration services and personalized Agora(s).

¹ aUPaEU's sister projects are Accelerate Future HEIs and CATALISI. aUPaEU actively collaborates with the two projects funded under the same call for the integration and implementation of acceleration services: European Research Area call (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01).

The aUPaEU Agora network lists the potential alliances that can be involved in the Agora process. The information stored in the Agora contacts module serves as a repository for any contacts that could potentially develop into leads. As of February 6th, 2025, the aUPaEU Agora network includes 613 individual stakeholders² from 48 alliances (Appendix A). Among these, 15 Alliances are tagged as potential Allies. Stakeholders listed in the aUPaEU Agora network receive regular updates and information through the project’s website, social media channels, and newsletter, while potential Allies—as a designated target group—receive tailored content (e.g., training videos, presentations, guides, and handbooks), participate in informative meetings, and are invited to internally organized events and collaborative communication/dissemination initiatives. In addition, 20 individuals are tagged as “Champions”. Champions are those who have co-developed or currently manage services within any Agora developed by aUPaEU. Their role is crucial in supporting the progressive expansion of the community, as they engage members of their own networks, who may themselves become new Champions.

As of the same date, the aUPaEU Agora network encompasses 142 Universities across 23 countries, of which 133 are located within the EU and 29 of them are in Widening countries (Appendix B). The list of Widening countries includes Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia³.

Table 1. Distribution of Universities listed in the aUPaEU Agora network by country

Country	Number of Universities	EU-27 (Y/N)	Widening country (Y/N)
Austria	4	Y	
Belgium	9	Y	
Czech Republic	4	Y	Y
Denmark	3	Y	
Finland	6	Y	
France	26	Y	
Germany	20	Y	
Greece	3	Y	Y
Hungary	3	Y	Y
Ireland	4	Y	
Italy	8	Y	
Latvia	1	Y	Y
Netherlands	8	Y	
Norway	1		
Poland	4	Y	Y

²Identification processes and taking into consideration a layered audience: university Alliances and ultimately individual users. Our user audiences are layered; on the one hand Alliances adopt the use of Agora and are users and managers of their services, on the other, end users are also individuals belonging to networks that have an Agora.

³ and all Associated Countries with equivalent characteristics in terms of R&I performance, as defined in *Horizon Europe - Work Programme 2023-2025. Widening participation and strengthening the European Research Area*. Part 11 - Pages 9-10.

Portugal	6	Y	Y
Romania	5	Y	Y
Serbia	1		Y
Spain	15	Y	
Sweden	4	Y	
Switzerland	2		
Turkey	2		Y
United Kingdom	3		
Total	142	133	29

2.1.2.2. Phases of Services Development

The communication and dissemination strategy is articulated around the different phases of development of acceleration services, as described in D2.1⁴ “Preliminary analysis and plan, outline of the acceleration services catalogue”. The plan is composed of seven steps, modelled on the five Design Thinking Phases, as shown in Table 2: Step 1. Stakeholder engagement and awareness building, which involves all WPs; Step 2. Requirement analysis and service design (WP2); Step 3. Data analysis; Step 4. Business process definition (WP4); Step 5. Implementation; Step 6. Testing and assessment; Step 7. Dissemination of knowledge and insights from the previous phases, in particular the services development and implementation phases. This promotes uptake within and beyond the original Higher Education Institutions, encourages continuous improvement and supports the development of new services.

The communication strategy follows the development of the services through the different phases. In the early phases WP7 establishes connections, exploring and developing synergies with other initiatives, promoting engagement with sister projects and other Alliances. This takes form in the shape of co-creation meetings, such as the ones taking place with our sister projects, with which we have established a concrete collaboration, written joint policy briefs and blog posts, shared social media campaigns and have featured in each other’s newsletters [see 3.1.3]. Then, the co-creation phase is shared on social media (specifically LinkedIn). To ensure this process, timely meetings with other WPs for content development and communication are held [see 3.2.1]. Once the services are implemented and mature, they are described on the project’s website under the “Acceleration Services” page [see 2.1.1] and they are relaunched on social media, subsequently training videos to guide both users and service managers are produced and uploaded on YouTube and Agora Support. During the iterative phases of testing, we’ll communicate the main feedback gathered; finally, after the testing results are incorporated to improve the service, the Viable Solution of the service will be

⁴ Timsit, P. N., Alcober, J., Bobeva, A., & Bruckert, F. (2024). aUPaEU D2.1 *Preliminary analysis and plan, outline of the acceleration services catalogue*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11614594>

disseminated. When the Viable Solution of Agora will be validated, it will be disseminated (e.g. final event), alongside its potential impact in accelerating HEIs institutional transformation.

Table 2. Five Design Thinking Phases with Corresponding Steps in aUPaEU methodology

Design Thinking Phase	Corresponding Step
Empathise	Step 1: Stakeholder engagement and awareness building (all) Step 2: Requirement analysis and service design (WP2) Step 7: Dissemination (WP7)
Define	Step 3: Data analysis (WP3) Step 4: Business process definition (WP4)
Ideate	Step 5: Implementation (WP5)
Prototype	Step 5: Implementation (WP5)
Test	Step 6: Testing and assessment (WP6)

2.1.2.3 Support Tools

As of February 24th, 2025, aUPaEU has successfully signed 17 User Agreements with 17 universities belonging to 3 Alliances (Unite!, EPICUR, EU GREEN). In view of the expansion of the project’s reach, and delivery of Agoras to new Alliances, a support strategy is being developed, specifically targeting these stakeholders (“Allies”, see 2.1.2.1).

The strategy includes actively promoting the platform to an extended audience and the development of tools to support the Alliances we involve. Thanks to these tools, aUPaEU is able to promote our services and provide the necessary support to the Alliances that receive an Agora in a way that is both sustainable and scalable for the project.

Among the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that have been identified by the consortium, as per Grant Agreement, there is *“An agora of acceleration services, made up of a platform, the catalogue and the processes that run it⁵”*. The training mentioned below, in the form of videos that explain how to use and manage the services, is deeply connected to the exploitation and sustainable scalability of the Agora, its services and its processes, as well as the Agora

⁵ Grant Agreement-101095314-aUPaEU, p. 12.

Support website and potentially Handbooks, for they ensure the sustainability of the project and of the Agoras developed in it.

New Alliances have at their disposal training videos, presentations, guides, and handbooks, all displayed on the new [Agora Support](#) website [see 2.2.1.2]. The ensemble of aUPaEU's WPs are currently involved in creating Handbooks, concise documents about each individual acceleration service. Each handbook will include information on how the service works, the resources required to establish and maintain the service, and all relevant organizational information. It is envisaged that the handbooks will be disseminated to new Alliances in the process of acquiring an Agora, to provide a full understanding of the services that can be implemented on Agora.

This strategy is enhanced by collaboration with the Alliances' communication officers to facilitate the promotion of their Agora's services to their audiences, as well as with sister projects [see paragraph 3.1 of this document]. The collaboration will take different forms depending on the internal structure of each Alliance and will be tailored to their needs and capacities, but the creation of templates or standard practices will increase scalability. For an example of communication collaboration, see the [landing page](#) for the Unite! Agora, co-developed between aUPaEU and Unite! The page presents Agora to potential individual users using short concise texts, rich visuals, and a presentation video, while also providing a link where users can access the platform.

2.1.2.4 Channels and Modes

As part of the strategy, to effectively communicate with our audiences, a number of channels and modes have been identified [see Table 5] and will be explained in the following chapters, including:

- Website
- Social media channels
- Training videos
- Publications
- Events participation.

Through the use of this approach, we align with the objectives of the strategy and ensure a comprehensive and effective engagement with our audiences, as explained in the following chapters.

2.2 Ongoing Activities

2.2.1 Achieved activities

The following are the activities that we have set out to carry out since D7.1 and that have been achieved:

- The project website features ad hoc sections for all aims [see 2.2.1]
- Protocols and templates for or the creation of an efficient communication pipeline have been created [see 3.2]
- aUPaEU has attended and organised events, conferences and workshops [see 2.2.6]
- The first press release has been published [see 2.2.5]
- Three newsletters have been sent [see 2.2.4]

2.2.1 Website

The project's public website was set up at the beginning of the aUPaEU project, in February 2023, and will be available for the duration of the project and beyond. The website is accessible at: [aUPaEU Project: Empowering Agoras for Widening Acceleration Services](#). It is the main channel for information, and it aims to reach all the project's audiences. The project website is continuously updated and enriched to ensure up to date information and efficient external communication.

The website, and social media banners along with it, underwent a revision in the summer of 2024, establishing a colour gradient based on the logo's colours, unifying the five colours, symbolizing the union and partnership of the five aUPaEU partner universities.

Most recently, to establish a recognisable identity for the project a Branding Guidelines and Identity Elements document (Appendix C) and a project tagline⁶ have been developed.

2.2.1.1 Website Pages

The structure of the website is as follows:

- Home
- Acceleration Services
- Blog
- News
- About us
- Results
- Agora Support
- Footer

The *Homepage* introduces the project, its main focus, its mission, and Agora of acceleration services.

The Acceleration Services page presents the acceleration services provided by aUPaEU's Agoras, initially through a short description of each service, including a link to individual pages for each acceleration service.

⁶ Tagline: *Empower universities. Accelerate Transformation. Step into Agora.*

All blog posts written by members of the project are available in the *Blog* page. Blog posts are a great way to showcase the work done by the Work Packages and to valorise the project results, which are adapted to the blog format, making them accessible to a wider audience. During 2024, thanks to a rotation system of writing blogs by each Work Package, blog activity has increased. As of March 2025, 10 blog posts have been published and simultaneously promoted on social media.

The *News* page contains all the aUPaEU news articles and visitors are invited to subscribe to the newsletter via a pop-up and to visit the *Newsletter* page, where there are dedicated pages for each newsletter. All news articles, and newsletters, are also shared on social media.

The *About Us* page provides an in-depth description of the project, which includes aUPaEU's goals, objectives and funding. The description is followed by a partners' map and their logos, team members' contacts and sister projects' introduction.

In the *Results* page, an easy to navigate menu provides links to deliverables, presentations, posters and video resources presented on Zenodo and YouTube.

The *Agora Support* page takes the visitor to the Agora Support website, a newly realized platform, launched in January 2025, designed to provide support materials to new alliances to which aUPaEU provides an Agora.

Finally, the footer displays the EU funding logo, the disclaimer⁷ and social media channels.

Fig. 1 & 2 Homepage

⁷ The project's website displays the disclaimer "Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.". On Agoras provided by aUPaEU to Alliances, two disclaimers are shown: one relates the content of Agora, which corresponds to the Alliance, and another for the aUPaEU project, which relates to Agora as a container platform. To ensure clarity, an additional text is then added: "The development and maintenance of the acceleration services and the Agora platform (container) are fully funded by the aUPaEU grant. The content displayed within this platform is independently funded, created, and managed by the featured organisations."

Fig. 3 Acceleration services page

Fig. 4 Blog page

Fig. 5 News page

Home Acceleration Services Blog **News** About Us Results Agora Support Sign in [Contact Us](#)

News

aUPaEU at the Grenoble Career Fair: Empowering Students' Research and Career

aUPaEU met with students at the Grenoble International Career Fair showcasing Agora's services designed for them to connect with research infrastructures, find internships and get involved in academic networks across Europe.

[Read more >](#)

aUPaEU at the Grenoble Research School: Digital Services for Researchers

Fig. 6 Results page

Home Acceleration Services Blog News About Us **Results** Agora Support Sign in [Contact Us](#)

Results

Resources

aUPaEU's project deliverables, posters and other materials are available on the [Zenodo](#) Community: Acceleration Services in support of the Institutional Transformation of Higher Education Institutions.

- Deliverables
- Posters
- Presentations
- Tutorials

Video tutorials are available to learn how to use our services

Fig. 7 Agora Support

Agora Support Submission form Events Contact us aUPaEU Sign In [Contact Us](#)

Agora support

To find resources, simply enter keywords in the search bar and use the filters to refine your results. You can narrow down options by level, acceleration service, type, user roles, or specific Agora projects. Once you find the desired resource, click to view. For any assistance, feel free to reach out to support.

Search... [Search](#)

Filter by Level... Basic Intermediate Advanced

Filter by Acceleration Service... Agoras Research Infrastructures Events Funding Coaching and Mentoring Stakeholder Management Showcases

Filter by Type... Rich text PDF Video Business Process Presentation External Links Poster

Filter by User...

2.2.1.2 Agora Support

Agora Support is a new website, live since January 2025, designed to support the new Alliances in the adoption of Agora and understanding the services. For easy access, it is integrated in the main project's website menu. Agora Support serves as a collaborative platform where both aUPaEU and experienced editors from established Alliances, such as Unite!, can share their expertise with newly integrated teams.

2.2.1.2 Website Analytics

Matomo Analytics was identified as the most suited tool for website analytics and was adopted in March 2024.

Website overview since Matomo's activation (6th of March 2024 – 18 of March 2025): 3.689 total visits, 5 min 8 sec average visit duration, 55% bounce rate after visiting one page, returning visits 2000 (54.21%). Visitors come from 6 continents, 48 countries and the ten countries with the most visits are: the US, Spain, Italy, Belgium, Germany, France, Netherlands, Poland, Finland, Ireland.

Fig. 8 Visits Overview in the timeframe between 06-03-2024 and 18-03-2025

Fig. 9 Returning and new behaviour

Frequency Overview

The five best performing pages of the aUPaEU website, without considering the login page, are: the Homepage, Acceleration Services, About us, News, Blog. This result is consistent with the efforts of directing traffic to these pages.

Fig. 10 Top five best performing pages

AUPAEU.WIDENING.EU | FROM 2024-03-06 TO 2025-03-18 | ALL VISITS | NEW UPDATE: MATOMO 5.3.1

Page titles

PAGE TITLE	PAGEVIEWS	UNIQUE PAGEVIEWS	BOUNCE RATE	AVG. TIME ON PAGE	EXIT RATE	AVG. PAGE LOAD TIME
aUPaEU Project: Empowering Agoras for Widening Acceleration Services	4,446	2,704	56%	00:01:39	75%	5.11s
acceleration-services aUPaEU agora	949	508	49%	00:01:08	40%	2.4s
Login aUPaEU agora	904	429	56%	00:00:54	84%	3.52s
About aUPaEU project	693	433	65%	00:01:47	52%	3.21s
news aUPaEU agora	533	262	42%	00:00:55	27%	1.46s
aUPaEU blog	475	285	52%	00:00:46	27%	4.4s

Fig. 11 Blog views

Title	Author	Blog	Website	No of Views
Acceleration Services	(UPC) aUPaEU, Jesus Alcober	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	534
Empowering Collaboration	(UPC) aUPaEU, Jesus Alcober	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	478
aUPaEU agoras	(UPC) aUPaEU, Jesus Alcober	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	453
Acceleration Services Outcomes	(UPC) aUPaEU, Jesus Alcober	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	438
Open Science, Acceleration Services and Institutional...	(KIT) Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Michael Anger	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	258
What are sister projects	(POLITO) Polytechnic University of Turin, Sofia Beatri...	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	160
Agora as Software	(AMU) Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Andrz...	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	157
First set of Policy implications and recommendations	(POLITO) Polytechnic University of Turin, Sofia Beatri...	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	103
Opening Agora to Companies	(KIT) Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Michael Anger	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	92
Facilitating Innovation	(KIT) Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Lauren Ciancio	aUPaEU blog	aUPaEU agora	60

Fig. 12 Geographical location of visitors

Visitor Map

Country

COUNTRY	VISITS
United States	1,019
Spain	823
Italy	701
Belgium	213
Germany	188
France	176
Netherlands	113
Poland	89
Finland	70
Ireland	59
Totals	3,689

2.2.2 Social Media Channels

aUPaEU is active on social media to maximize the project actions undertaken and to engage in a two-way dialogue with stakeholders. Its channels are:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/aUPaEU>, active since June 2023.
- X (formerly Twitter): <https://x.com/WideningEU>, active since December 2022.
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@aUPaEUproject>, active since October 2023.

Three fixed tags have been identified and are always used on LinkedIn: #HEIs #accelerationservices #HigherEducationTransformation.

On our social media channels, we share content aimed at the various audience segments outlined in Table 5. This includes content designed to increase the visibility of the project, highlight its achievements, display the activities carried out, and showcase the Agora platform with its acceleration services for HEI transformation. In particular, when promoting our services, we focus on engaging the “Allies” audience, since they are the ones that have adopted or would adopt Agora and its services.

2.2.2.1.1 LinkedIn and X

In 2024, WP7 established a pattern of posting approximately every 10 days on LinkedIn and X. Throughout the last year, contents, while mainly going hand in hand with website publications, have focused on multiple aspects: spanning from goals and actions of each WP to the aims and outputs of the project, to the acceleration services being developed and delivered through Agora. Specific campaigns include an ongoing promotion of aUPaEU's acceleration services, and one to promote joint activities with sister projects [see 3.1.3]. As mentioned in 2.1.1, effectively disseminating the catalogue of acceleration services is central for the project and promoting and explaining the individual services is an activity carried out throughout the project's lifetime, also through campaigns on social media with posts and videos.

In early 2024 a social media campaign was established in collaboration with the Unite! Alliance, aimed at promoting the use of the services available on the Unite! Agora.

At the present moment, doubts about the use of X (formerly known as Twitter) are being raised. Massive user migration, low performance indicators, misalignment with Unite!'s and Epicur's decision to leave X, and since becoming a controversial platform, we must ask ourselves if it loses strategic value. aUPaEU is evaluating a potential transition to BlueSky.

2.2.2.1.2 YouTube

On YouTube, aUPaEU's most relevant and continuous publications consist of training videos. As mentioned in 2.1.2, part of the strategy for ensuring the sustainability of the project both during its funding period and afterwards, for all the new Alliances using Agoras, aUPaEU training videos have been identified as a key tool. Training videos are technical in nature and guide step-by-step the viewer through either the use or the management of the services offered. To this end two playlists have been created: "[A user guide for the Agora platform services](#)", for the end user and "[A manager's guide to Agora services](#)" for the management on the Alliance or university's side. The videos are available the YouTube channel, are relaunched on social media, are findable in the "Results" page of the website, and are displayed on Agora Support to offer appropriate support to new managers of services in the different Alliances receiving Agoras.

2.2.2.1.3 Social Media Analytics

LinkedIn

As of March 18, 2025, aUPaEU has 401 followers on LinkedIn and posted a total of 129 posts, of which: 29 in 2023, 83 in 2024 and 17 in 2025.

In the last 365 days: 34.857 Impressions, 938 reactions, 685 page visualisations, 347 unique visitors.

Fig. 13 LinkedIn overview in the timeframe between 18-03-2024 and 17-03-2025

Highlights

Data for 3/18/2024 - 3/17/2025

34,857
Impressions

938
Reactions

21
Comments

9
Reposts

The project has adopted the Metricool social media management tool to access automatically downloadable reports in multiple formats, analytics with unlimited historical data since activation, management of all social media accounts and scheduling tools. Since Metricool's activation, in the last four months (18 November 2024 – 18 March 2025), the LinkedIn account has received: 13.81K page impressions, 1.769 post interactions, 21 posts, 362 reactions, 1.377 clicks.

Fig. 14 LinkedIn page impressions the timeframe between 18-11-2024 and 18-03-2025

Fig. 15 & 16 LinkedIn posts' performance in the timeframe between 18-11-2024 and 18-03-2025

X (formerly Twitter)

As of March 18th, 2025, aUPaEU's X account has 118 overall posts. For the last 100 posts: 87 average views per post, 1.65%, average engagement rate, 1 average engagement per post.

Fig. 17 & 18 X overview

YouTube

Up until March 18, 2025, the project's YouTube channel has published a total of 15 videos. Overview through the channel's lifetime (9 Oct 2023 – 18 Mar 2025): 15 videos, 11 followers, 1.1K views, 26.2 hours of viewing time, 12.9 K Impressions, 1 min 26 sec average viewing time, 88.7 % of the viewers are not subscribed; 9.1% of video views are coming from LinkedIn. Figure 20 displays the five most viewed videos on the channel.

Fig. 19 YouTube Lifetime Overview

Your channel has had 1,085 views so far

Fig. 20 YouTube Top 5 most viewed videos

Content	Average view duration	Views
1 Revolutionising Higher Education: Unveilin... 12 Dec 2023	0:53 (39.7%)	352
2 How to Contact Research Infrastructures i... 17 Oct 2024	0:57 (52.0%)	139
3 Aida: Revolutionising Agoras with Intellige... 23 Jan 2024	0:41 (38.5%)	91
4 How to contact a proposal in Unite! Agora ... 29 Aug 2024	0:36 (36.5%)	87
5 Workshop "Presenting the concept and the... 23 Feb 2024	10:11 (10.5%)	69

2.2.3 Zenodo

Zenodo has been identified as the ideal platform for centralized project publications. aUPaEU's project deliverables, posters and other materials are available on [Zenodo](#). This ensures that our project outputs are accessible to the wider scientific community and contributes to the principles of Open Science by promoting transparency and sharing of research findings. Thus far approved deliverables have been uploaded on Zenodo, alongside

posters and presentations. We have two Zenodo communities: [Acceleration Services in support of the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions](#) and [aUPaEU - A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities](#). The first community has been created to showcase project publications jointly with aUPaEU's sister projects, i.e. CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI, which are funded under [the same call](#) as aUPaEU. While the joint community allows us to amplify projects' results, in early 2025 the project has opened the new Zenodo page specifically dedicated to aUPaEU: [aUPaEU - A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities](#).

2.2.4 Newsletters

E-newsletters are issued to the aUPaEU community to report on the latest activities and news content. The newsletters are sent through one of the Agora tools for stakeholder management: the "Email marketing" tool, which allows managers to create newsletters directly on the platform and send them to dedicated mailing lists. Recipients receive the newsletter via email from the address agora@widening.eu, and the newsletters are always available online on the project website under [Newsletters | aUPaEU agora](#).

Three newsletters have been sent over the course of the first two years of the project.

The first newsletter was sent on the 3rd of April 2024, and it introduced the aUPaEU project, our mission, purpose and goals in the Higher Education landscape, focusing on: project presentation, the first aUPaEU workshop, blog posts about Agoras and included a presentation of sister projects.

The second edition of the newsletter was sent on the 19th of July 2024, focused on the key deliverables produced over the first year and a half, including an overview of the Agora platform, best practices and acceleration services.

The third newsletter, originally planned for December 2024, was rescheduled for February 2025 in order to include relevant content about the General Assembly, which took place in late January; it focused on: the launch of Agora Support and project goals for the new year. The third edition, sent on the 13th of February, included: 2025 projections, aUPaEU's acceleration services, news articles, upcoming events, new blog posts, Agora support and sister projects features.

Table 3. Newsletter metrics

Newsletter Edition	N. of recipients	Opening rate
1 st Newsletter	156	56 %
2 nd Newsletter	157	63 %
3 rd Newsletter	174	56%

2.2.5 Additional materials

The project has produced other materials that don't necessarily fit the previous categories, listed here:

- First press release: 20th of October 2023: <https://aupaeu.widening.eu/press-release>. The press release is also available in the local languages on partner universities' websites: [KIT](#), [UPC](#), [PoliTO](#), [Grenoble INP-UGA](#), [Unite!](#). It was picked up by local Italian press: [Agenparl - Agenzia di Stampa Parlamentare](#), [Il Torinese](#).
- Poster [aUPaEU Agora](#): presented at the German State Ministry of Science, Research and the Arts of Baden-Württemberg, in March 2024.
- Poster [Unite! Agora for All](#): originally presented during the IX Unite! Dialogue at TU Graz and then During the X Unite! Dialogue in Darmstadt at TU Darmstadt.
- Flyers, distributed at EAIE 2024.
- Conference paper: [Exploring the Implementation of Acceleration Services in Higher Education: A Case Study of Unite! Agora as a Transformative Platform](#), presented at the 2024 EUNIS Congress in June, and published on Jan 13, 2025. DOI: 10.29007/zjjj.

2.2.6 Events

2.2.6.1 Internally Organised Events

aUPaEU hosted its first workshop, "[Presenting the concept and the implementation of the agora](#)", on January 26, 2024.

This "Initial workshop", originally proposed for December 2023, coincides with Milestone 7 (ML7) and its organization started in November 2023. The event was organised so that project members could attend in person, at Politecnico di Torino, Italy, for the General Assembly on Jan 25. In addition, an [online workshop](#) was held on Zoom, on Jan 26, 2024.

The workshop was structured in two parts: the first one to present both the concept and the functioning of an Agora, and the second one to allow for the audience's involvement.

During this second part of the workshop, participants answered questions, using a collaborative tool to collect ideas about Agora and the acceleration services. The online audience was composed of over 90 people. Through the registration process (which involved email invitations to individuals belonging to core and extended groups using a registration form sent, via email marketing, and promoted on social media), over one hundred new contacts were collected and added to Agora. The questions posed to the audience were useful

to collect answers and insights into higher education members' ideas, which have proven to be instrumental for WP3's analysis [see D3.1.2⁸, Appendix 1].

Fig. 21 First Workshop

2.2.6.2 Externally Organised Events

Participation in externally organised events is a key aspect of the dissemination of aUPaEU's results, for this reason, events such as conferences, webinars, and workshops are continuously mapped. This activity is also carried out jointly with sister projects, to maximize impact [see 3.1.3].

In particular, as of March 31st 2025, aUPaEU has participated in 10 externally organized events. (Table 4). A detailed description of the impact generated (in terms of number of attendees, target audience, contacts generated and follow up actions) follows.

Table 4. Externally Organised Events

Date	Event	Organizer	n. attendees (approx.)	Target audience
27-29 February 2024	IX Unite! Dialogue	Unite!	400	University professionals, including staff, faculty, academic associates, representatives of the Unite! Alliance
8 March 2024	New Beginnings: Ministry of	Ministry of Science,	200	University Rectors, Professors and

⁸ Pending approval

	Science, Research and the Arts Baden-Württemberg	Research and the Arts Baden-Württemberg		representatives of government and politics
7 June 2024	EUNIS 2024 Congress	EUNIS - European University Information Systems	300	University professionals - including IT staff, academic leaders, and administrators -involved in digital transformation and European initiatives
17-20 September 2024	EAIE 2024	EAIE - European Association for International Education	7200	Representatives from European University alliances.
24-26 September 2024	X Unite! Dialogue	Unite!	400	University professionals, including staff, faculty, academic associates, representatives of the Unite! Alliance
18 October 2024	Unite! Research School	Unite!	200	PhD and Masters students, as well as researchers from the Unite! Universities.
28 November 2024	International Career Fair	Grenoble INP-UGA	16 attendees to aUPaEU session	Late-stage students from Unite! Universities
24 January 2025	Work Package 9 Infrastructure Staff Week	EU GREEN	40	University professionals, including staff, faculty, academic associates, representatives of the EU GREEN alliance.
25-28 February 2025	XI Unite! Dialogue	Unite!	400	University professionals, including staff, faculty, academic associates, representatives of the Unite! Alliance
30 January 2025	Learning from the 1st edition of the European Higher Education Sector Scoreboard and looking at the future of EHESO	EHESO	100	Alliances, consortia, HEIs and experts involved in ERA policies

- IX Unite! Dialogue, February 2024, TU Graz, Austria. The aUPaEU project Coordinator, Jesus Alcober, presented the Unite! Agora in a pitch presentation and showcased the poster "[Empowering Collaboration: Unite! Agora for All](#)" as part of the "Unite! What's in it for me?" community event. The event involved approx. 400 attendees. The target audience included University professionals, including staff, faculty, academic associates, representatives of the Unite! Alliance. Contacts were taken to improve stakeholder mapping in the launch phase of the aUPaEU project. Follow up actions involved a targeted communication campaign.
- [New Beginnings: Ministry of Science, Research and the Arts Baden-Württemberg](#), March 8, 2024, Stuttgart, Germany. Michael Zacherle (KIT) was invited to deliver a presentation and present a poster for aUPaEU to the Minister and members of University Rectorates and professors in Stuttgart at the German State Ministry of Science, Research and the Arts of Baden-Württemberg. The event involved approx. 200 attendees. The target audience included University Rectors, Professors and representatives of government and politics. Contacts were taken with members of the EPICUR alliance to improve stakeholder mapping in the launch phase of the aUPaEU project. Follow up actions involved a targeted communication campaign.
- EUNIS24 Congress, June 7, 2024, in Athens, Greece. Juan Lopez Rubio (UPC) successfully submitted the paper [Exploring the Implementation of Acceleration Services in Higher Education: A Case Study of Unite! Agora as a Transformative Platform](#) and presented it. The event involved approx. 300 attendees. The target audience comprised University professionals - including IT staff, academic leaders, and administrators - involved in digital transformation and European initiatives. Contacts were taken with professionals from Universitat Oberta de Catalunya - Open University of Catalonia, (among which, the responsible for Education Technologies architectures); and with the co-founder of Academic Portals, a startup in EdTech offering digital solutions for data governance and content access to HEIs. Follow up actions involved maintaining contact to discuss Higher Education Reference Models (HERM) in the context of aUPaEU.
- EAIE 2024, 17-20 September 2024, Toulouse, France. Although aUPaEU did not actively take part in the conference, the Project Coordinator participated and, on this occasion, laid the foundations for fruitful collaborations with new Alliances. The event involved approx. 7200 attendees. The target audience included numerous representatives from European university alliances. Contacts were taken with professionals and representatives (coordinators) from CHARM-EU, EUTOPIA, INGENIUM University, UNIVERSEH, EU GREEN, 4EU+, CIVICA, SEA-EU, EULIST, EUT+, FORTHEM, ENGAGE.EU, EU-CONEXUS and EPICUR. We met with them and these conversations focused on exploring collaboration opportunities and showcasing the potential of the Agora platforms from the aUPaEU project. The conference provided the opportunity to engage meaningfully a wide and selected range of potential Allies and users of Agoras. We followed up with these contacts to invite them to develop and test tailored Agoras.

- X Unite! Dialogue, September 2024, TU Darmstadt, Germany. Jesus Alcober and WP2 Leaders hosted a [brainstorming session](#), engaging with the coordinators and members of the Unite! Widening Project and of the IRIS network. An updated version of the poster titled "[Empowering Collaboration: Unite! Agora for All](#)" was showcased as part of the "Unite! World Café" community event. The event involved approx. 400 attendees. The target audience included University professionals, including staff, faculty, academic associates, representatives of the Unite! Alliance. Contacts were taken with professionals and representatives of the Unite! Widening Project and of the IRIS network. Follow up actions included the potential development of services for Unite! Widening, in particular concerning research infrastructures.
- [Unite! Research School](#), 18 October 2024, Grenoble, France. aUPaEU WP2 leaders hosted a brainstorming session at the Unite! Research School in Grenoble, aimed at gaining insights into researchers' needs and get relevant feedback to improve [Unite! Agora](#) digital services. The event involved approx. 200 attendees. The target audience comprised PhD and Master students, as well as researchers from the Unite! Universities. Contacts included researchers and project representatives from Unite! Universities such as TU Darmstadt, and TU Graz. Follow up actions were taken towards improving the Unite! Agora digital services, by integrating relevant feedback in the Agora services portfolio (in particular, funding opportunities, internships, and research and innovation proposals).
- [International Career Fair](#) organised by Grenoble INP-UGA, 28 November 2024, Online. aUPaEU, WP 6, had the opportunity to organise a "digital Agora stand", aimed at students looking to expand their academic horizons. This event constituted a first coaching day, providing a basis for testing and maintaining users engaged in aUPaEU's acceleration services. The target audience mainly comprised late-stage students from Unite! Universities. 16 attendees registered to the session. Contacts were established with students from Grenoble INP-UGA, including Erasmus students, and other Unite! Universities as potential users, showcasing opportunities and gathering feedback on the first services developed by aUPaEU (among which: internships, Doctoral courses, research and innovation proposals, research infrastructures). Follow up actions included an analysis of the feedback received on the selected services, with findings reported to other WPs to support services improvement.
- EU Green Alliance's "Work Package 9 Infrastructure Staff Week", 24 January 2025, Angers, France. aUPaEU WP5 leaders were invited to present the project, the Agora, and a prototype of an Agora for EU Green. The event involved approx. 40 attendees. The target audience was composed by University professionals, including staff, faculty, academic associates, representatives of the EU GREEN alliance. Contacts were taken with infrastructure staff to include them in test teams of the EU GREEN alliance. We followed up by actively supporting the test teams of the EUGREEN alliance throughout the co-development of a tailored Agora.
- [XI Unite! Dialogue](#), 25-28 February 2025, UPC, Barcelona, Spain. aUPaEU presented a poster, video presentation, a session organized by WP2 including guided focus group with Dialogue participants, and also had a support room set up for easy access to technical support. The event involved approx. 400 attendees. The target audience

included University professionals, including staff, faculty, academic associates, representatives of the Unite! alliance. Contacts were taken with staff, faculty and researchers from the participating Universities, to whom we offered Agora coaching and support to increase the number of potential users and increase the quality of engagement. Follow up actions involved a targeted communication campaign.

- [Learning from the 1st edition of the European Higher Education Sector Scoreboard and looking at the future of EHESO](#), 30 January 2025, organised by EHESO, online. Leaders of policy briefing task within aUPaEU attended the online conference. The event involved approx. 100 attendees. The target audience included Alliances, consortia, HEIs and experts involved in ERA policies. Contacts were taken with researchers at Joanneum Research and representatives of EHESO The European Higher Education Sector Observatory, to set up a collaboration and increase the relevance of the aUPaEU project results. A specific discussion involved the possibility to access the EHESO scoreboard data through open APIs and use it for future policy briefs. Follow up actions are expected after a discussion of public access between the EHESO project team and the contracting authority and the possibility to use relevant data from the EHESO scoreboard for policy briefs.

Fig. 22 Michael Zacherle at the German State Ministry

Fig. 23 Jesus Alcober at the IX Unite! Dialogue

2.3 Planned Activities (M28-M60)

2.3.1 Updated Plan of Upcoming Communication and Dissemination Activities

The period between M28 and M60 encompasses the third, fourth, and fifth year of the project. Below is a concise description of the main planned communication and dissemination activities.

The website, as the central channel for disseminating aUPaEU's contents, its acceleration services, and all other activities carried out in the context of the project, will continue to undergo constant updates. Analytics tools, such as Matomo and Metricool, will assess the website's performance.

Particular importance regarding the website will be placed on:

- enriching the Acceleration Services page, with respect to the six areas of the HEI transformation agenda these belong to (capacity, infrastructure, and resource sharing; researcher career attractiveness; collaboration with R&I ecosystem actors; open science; societal outreach; and gender equality)
- maintaining the regular production of blog posts
- showcasing results.

2.3.1.1 Planned Internally Organised and Externally Organised Events

The identification of, and participation in externally organised events will continue throughout the project's lifetime.

- Internally organised: Mid-term workshop (ML8) in M36 and Final Event (M57).
- Externally organised:
 - INORMS Congress, 6-8 May 2025, Madrid, Spain. Accepted abstract for two round tables: "[Open Agora: Empowering Transnational Collaboration](#)"; "[Agoras' AI-Powered Research Management](#)".
 - UIIN Conference, 10-12 June 2025, Amsterdam, Netherlands. Accepted poster.
 - Epicur Forum 2025, 2-3 June 2025, Odense, Denmark. Active participation in the Epicur Forum is being pursued.

The following table represents the communication and dissemination activities planned for the remainder of the project. This table is an update of Table 2.1 in Deliverable D7.1.

Table 5. Updated plan of upcoming aUPaEU communication and dissemination activities

Activity	Purpose	Audience	Timing
Website	Being the main channel for distributing content, services and activities, it will be constantly updated. A set of Matomo analytics instruments will continue to be used to track and to report the engagement and the number of visits to the website.	University Alliances (with particular focus on their managers and decision-makers) (and within Alliances the single Universities and research institutions), single Universities and research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances, Citizens, Public administrations, Industry and businesses, policy makers.	M1 - M60
Social media	LinkedIn, X (formerly known as Twitter) and YouTube accounts will continue to be regularly animated to maximize the project actions undertaken and to engage in a two-way dialogue with core and extended stakeholders and end users. Analytics, such as Metricool	University Alliances (and within Alliances the single Universities and research institutions), with strong focus on "Allies", single Universities and research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances, Citizens, Public	M6 - M60

	<p>reports, will be used to track and report engagement on social media channels.</p> <p>Presence on platforms alternative to X will be evaluated.</p>	<p>administrations, Industry and businesses, policy makers.</p>	
E-newsletters	<p>E-newsletters will be issued to the aUPaEU community to report on the latest activities and news.</p>	<p>University Alliances (and within Alliances the single Universities and research institutions), single Universities and research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances, policy makers.</p>	<p>M48, M60</p>
Handbooks	<p>Handbooks for individual Agora acceleration services. Handbooks are documents that explain acceleration services in a comprehensive way. They are tools for effectively presenting services from different angles, not detailed technical documentation.</p>	<p>Managers and decision-makers from University Alliances (and within Alliances the single Universities and research institutions) that are adopting Agora or are interested in doing so.</p>	<p>M30 - 60</p>
Publications and press releases	<p>Two more press releases will be issued: one in the second half of the project's existence and one to highlight the project's results. News articles (web news) and dedicated social media activities will be issued on the occasion of the workshop events.</p> <p>At least two more articles will be published in peer-reviewed</p>	<p>University Alliances (and within Alliances the single Universities and research institutions), single Universities and research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances, Citizens, Public administrations, Industry and businesses, policy makers.</p>	<p>M30, M36, M48, M60</p>

	journals and specialized publications (open access).		
Internally organised events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mid-term workshop (ML8): presenting the concept and the implementation of the MVS of the agora (M36), possibly in the occasion of a relevant EC event, (e.g., European R&I days). - Final event (M57) 	University Alliances (and within Alliances the single Universities and research institutions), with strong focus on “Allies”, single Universities and research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances, Citizens, Public administrations, Industry and businesses, Policy makers.	M36, M57
Coaching events	aUPaEU will provide a series of coaching days for user groups on acceleration services. Coaching will be based on the acceleration services catalogue, and they will provide a basis for testing and maintaining users engaged in aUPaEU’s acceleration services on multiple Agoras.	Current and potential users of aUPaEU acceleration services, such as faculty, staff and students.	M23 - M45
Zenodo	Zenodo is the ideal platform for centralized project publications. aUPaEU's project deliverables, posters and other materials are available on Zenodo, ensuring our outputs are accessible to the	University Alliances (and within Alliances the single Universities and research	M13- M60

	scientific community, and contributing to Open Science by promoting transparency and sharing.	institutions), policy makers.	
Externally organised Events	aUPaEU will participate in a number of events not organised by the project itself, to raise awareness, engage and draw-in potential users. These events include conferences (e.g. the EARMA conference and INORMS Congress), Unite! Dialogues, Epicur Forum, EUNIS Congress, workshops organised by other Alliances or projects.	Potential future users of aUPaEU acceleration services, such as Faculty, staff and students belonging to University Alliances single Universities and research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances.	M9 - M60

3 Synergies with Other Projects and Internal Actors

All Work Packages are actively involved in engaging with other Alliances and projects, to develop collaborations and with the ultimate goal of delivering Agoras to them and to leverage complementarities. Such activities involve meetings with representatives from: EU GREEN Alliance, CIVIS Alliance, EUTOPIA Alliance, EUCOR Alliance, EDUXS project, FOR EU, CHARM EU Alliance, Unite! Widening project, CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI projects.

3.1 Engagement with Sister Projects

3.1.1 Who are Sister Projects

Funded under the [same call](#) of the European Research Area are aUPaEU's sister projects, [Accelerate Future HEI](#) and [CATALISI](#). The three projects share the same values and objectives aiming to improve Higher Education Institutions, accelerating their institutional reform processes.

Given our complementarities, we decided to collaborate and work in synergy, starting from joint policy briefs deliverables, to communication and dissemination coordination.

3.1.2 Shared Branding

A unique branding has been developed to use in joint digital creativities. This includes specific colours (#4caf50 #64dd17), two shades of green, a colour that no single project has in their logos, making it different enough to be identifiable as belonging to initiatives that are shared. To embody the shared objective of supporting Higher Education Institution's transformation, we crafted a tagline through which audiences can easily identify common initiatives: *Together for HEI transformation*.

3.1.3 Joint Activities

Joint activities with sister projects include:

- Monthly communication meetings
- Joint social media campaigns
- Shared branding development
- Shared event spreadsheet for synergic participation
- Joint policy deliverables
- INORMS Congress joint submission, to work towards the co-creation of one or more services.

A shareholder folder was established in April 2024 and is used to share documents between the projects. The communication Work Packages of the sister projects have been meeting regularly, once every month to coordinate on communication strategies. Among the communication synergies: joint social media campaigns have been developed (3) as well as joint blog posts (2); reciprocal features in each project's website and newsletters (3); shared online [Zenodo](#) community; continuous identification of events to jointly participate in (most recently coordination for INORMS 2025 Congress joint submission).

3.2 Engagement with Internal Actors

3.2.1 Internal Coordination

Coordination within the project team members and the partner universities is fundamental for effectively communicating project activities and results. For this reason, there are constant information flows between WP7 and all other WPs. These include written communications, meetings, and shared files. A schedule of meetings every month between WP7 and each single WP has been established. As the project matures, planning and sharing information on relevant events will be increasingly important for communication and dissemination efforts.

The identification of external events is an ongoing activity across all Work Packages throughout the life of the project. Tracking these events and coordinating with sister projects has been identified as a critical task for the aUPaEU project. To streamline internal

communication, a file has been created to monitor these events. In addition, the file is integrated with a similar system shared with sister projects to facilitate the identification of potential synergies and opportunities for joint participation. Moreover, Work Package Leaders (WPLs) receive email updates informing them of upcoming events and relevant submission deadlines.

In regard to the five partner universities, communication contacts at each institution receive emails to disseminate information within their respective universities.

3.2.2 Internal Materials

In order to facilitate effective communication and ensure consistency across all project activities, a variety of internal materials have been developed. These materials include internal presentations, which are designed to provide clear, structured information for team members and stakeholders. Additionally, templates for slides and videos have been created to maintain a cohesive visual identity in all project-related communications.

To further support the coordination of efforts, an online spreadsheet has been implemented to track upcoming events and to ensure that the most suited communication materials are provided. Similarly, a dissemination spreadsheet has been established to monitor and organise dissemination activities, helping to ensure that information is shared in a timely and strategic manner. These tools collectively serve to enhance the project's internal processes, streamline communication, and maintain alignment within the project.

WP7 has effectively built on the initial communication and dissemination plan. It has integrated new tools and activities to further strengthen the project and meet emerging needs. As a result, the entire aUPaEU project is now better equipped to tackle the remaining tasks, and the visibility of the project has increased, strengthening its impact and reach.

APPENDIX A

Alliances currently listed in the aUPaEU Agora network

- (1EUROPE) Una Europa
- (4EU+) 4EU+ European University Alliance
- (ARQUS) Arqus European University
- (Aurora Alliance) Aurora Alliance
- (CHARMEU) Challenge-Driven, Accessible, Research-based and Mobile European University
- (Circle U.) Circle U. European University
- (CIVICA) The European University of Social Sciences
- (CIVIS) CIVIS - a European Civic University
- (E3UDRES2) Engaged and Entrepreneurial European University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions
- (EC2U) European Campus of City-Universities
- (ECIU+) ECIU University
- (EDUC) European Digital UniverCity
- (EELISA) European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance
- (ENGAGE.EU) The European University engaged in societal change
- (ENHANCE) European Universities of Technology Alliance
- (EPICUR) European Partnership for an Innovative Campus Unifying Regions
- (ERUA) European Reform University Alliance
- (EU GREEN) European University alliance for sustainability: responsible GRowth, inclusive Education and ENvironment
- (EU-CONEXUS) European University for Smart Urban Coastal Sustainability
- (EUGLOH 2.0) European University Alliance for Global Health
- (EULIST) European Universities Linking Society and Technology
- (EUNICE) EUNICE - European University for Customised Education
- (EUniWell) European University for WellBeing
- (EUPeace) European University for Peace, Justice, and Inclusive Societies
- (EURECA-PRO) The European University Alliance on Responsible Consumption and Production
- (EuroTeQ) EuroTeQ Engineering University
- (EUTOPIA) European Universities Transforming to an Open Inclusive Academy
- (FILMEU) FILMEU - The European Universities Alliance for Film and Media Arts
- (FORTHEM) Fostering Outreach within European Regions, Transnational Higher Education and Mobility
- (INGENIUM) INGENIUM – European University
- (NeurotechEU) European University of Brain and Technology
- (OpenEU) The learner-centred, inclusive, digital and green Open European University for the strengthening of the European Higher Education Area
- (PIONEER) The European University for Future Cities
- (RUN-EU) Regional University Network – European University
- (T4E) Transform4Europe – The European University for Knowledge Entrepreneurs
- (ULYSSEUS) Ulysseus: An open to the world, persons-centred and entrepreneurial European University for the citizenship of the future
- (UNITA) UNITA - Universitas Montium

(Unite!) University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering

(UNIVERSEH) European Space University of Earth and Humanity

(YUFE 2030) Young Universities for the Future of Europe Alliance

NEOLAIa

U!REKA

(EUNICE) EUNICE - European University for Customised Education

(ULYSSEUS) Ulysseus: An open to the world, persons-centred and entrepreneurial European University for the citizenship of the future

(UNITA) UNITA - Universitas Montium

APPENDIX B

Universities listed in the aUPaEU Agora network

University	Country	Widening
(Aalto) Aalto University	Finland	
(AEGEAN) University of the Aegean	Greece	Y
(AGH) AGH University of Krakow	Poland	Y
(AMU) Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań	Poland	Y
(AMU) D'AIX MARSEILLE UNIVERSITE	France	
(ATU) Atlantic Technological University	Ireland	
(AUTH) ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI	Greece	Y
(Avans) Avans University of Applied Sciences	Netherlands	
(BOKU) UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	Austria	
(ciencias ulisboa) Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa		
(Ciências ULisboa)	Portugal	Y
(CUni) Charles University	Czech Republic	Y
(DAAD) German Academic Exchange Service	Germany	
(DTU) Technical University of Denmark	Denmark	
(ELTE) Eötvös Loránd University	Hungary	Y
(ETH Zürich) ETH Zurich	Switzerland	
(EUR) Erasmus University Rotterdam	Netherlands	
(FUB) Freie Universität Berlin	Germany	
(Grenoble INP - UGA) Grenoble Institute of Technology	France	
(HEYL) University of Helsinki	Finland	
(HOGENT) University College Ghent	Belgium	
(INPT) National Polytechnic Institute of Toulouse	France	
(IPCA) Polytechnic Institute of Cávado and Ave	Portugal	Y
(ISAE-SUPAERO) Institut Supérieur de l'Aeronautique et de l'Espace (ISAE-SUPAERO)	France	
(İTU) Istanbul Technical University	Turkey	Y
(JAMK) JAMK University of Applied Sciences	Finland	
(JGU) Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz	Germany	
(JLU) University of Giessen	Germany	
(JY) University of Jyväskylä	Finland	
(KIT) Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Germany	
(KTH) KTH Royal Institute of Technology	Sweden	
(KU LEUVEN) KU Leuven	Belgium	
(LARO) University of La Rochelle	France	
(LIU) Linköping University	Sweden	
(LMU MUENCHEN) Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München	Germany	
(m) Nantes Université	France	
(m) Paris 8 University	France	
(m) Universidade Lusófona	Portugal	Y
(m) Université Côte d'Azur	France	
(m) University of Burgundy	France	

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(m) University of Poitiers	France	
(MOLE) Montanuniversität Leoben	Austria	
(OSU) University of Ostrava	Czech Republic	Y
(PLUS) University of Salzburg	Austria	
(POLITO) Polytechnic University of Turin	Italy	
(RWTH Aachen) RWTH Aachen University	Germany	
(SCIENCESPO) Sciences Po	France	
(SDU) University of Southern Denmark	Denmark	
(SOUN) Sorbonne Université	France	
(STPUAS) St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences	Austria	
(STUN) Stockholm University	Sweden	
(TAKO) Tampere University	Finland	
(TCD) Trinity College Dublin	Ireland	
(TU Da) Technical University of Darmstadt	Germany	
(TU GRAZ) Graz University of Technology	Austria	
(TU/e) Eindhoven University of Technology	Netherlands	
(TUB) Technische Universität Berlin	Germany	
(TUM) Technical University of Munich	Germany	
(U.PORTO) Universidade do Porto	Portugal	Y
(UAB) Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	Spain	
(UANTWERPEN) University of Antwerp	Belgium	
(UB) University of Belgrade	Serbia	Y
(UB) University of Bristol	United Kingdom	
(UB) University of Bucharest	Romania	Y
(UBI) University of Beira Interior	Portugal	Y
(UCC) University College Cork	Ireland	
(UCD) University College Dublin	Ireland	
(UCLL) University Colleges Leuven-Limburg	Belgium	
(UCLouvain) UCLouvain	Belgium	
(UCM) Universidad Complutense de Madrid	Spain	
(UCPH) University of Copenhagen	Denmark	
(UEC) Universidad Europea de Madrid	Spain	
(UEDIN) University of Edinburgh	United Kingdom	
(UEX) Universidad de Extremadura	Spain	
(UFC) University of Franche-Comté	France	
(UFR) University of Freiburg	Germany	
(UGR) Universidad de Granada	Spain	
(UHA) University of Upper Alsace	France	
(UHEI) Heidelberg University	Germany	
(UHU) Universidad de Huelva	Spain	
(UJA) Universidad de Jaén	Spain	
(ULB) Université Libre de Bruxelles	Belgium	
(ULBS) Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu	Romania	Y
(ULEI) Leiden University	Netherlands	
(ULISBOA) University of Lisbon	Portugal	Y

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(UMa) Universidade da Madeira	Spain	
(UMA) University of Mannheim	Germany	
(UMH) Universitat de Miguel Hernández d'Elx	Spain	
(UMR) Philipps University of Marburg	Germany	
(UNamur) University of Namur	Belgium	
(UNI) University of Oslo	Norway	
(UNIBO) University of Bologna	Italy	
(UNIC) University of Nicosia	Cyprus	Y
(UNICA) University of Cagliari	Italy	
(UniGe) University of Genoa	Italy	
(UNIPV) University of Pavia	Italy	
(UNISA) University of Salerno	Italy	
(UNISTRA) University of Strasbourg	France	
(UNITS) University of Trieste	Italy	
(UNIV PARIS1) Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne	France	
(UNIV SMB) Université Savoie Mont Blanc	France	
(UNIV TOULOUSE) Université de Toulouse	France	
(Universität Bielefeld) Bielefeld University	Germany	
(Université Gustave Eiffel) Université Gustave Eiffel	France	
(UNJA) Jagiellonian University	Poland	Y
(UNMA) Maastricht University	Netherlands	
(UNPA) Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	France	
(UNTW) University of Twente	Netherlands	
(UOC) Universitat Oberta de Catalunya	Spain	
(UOV) Universidad de Oviedo	Spain	
(UP) Universitatea Din Petrosani	Romania	Y
(UP) University of Potsdam	Germany	
(UPC) Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	Spain	
(UPM) Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Spain	
(UPNA) Universidad Publica de Navarra	Spain	
(UPPA) Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour	France	
(UPSaclay) University of Paris-Saclay	France	
(UPT) Polytechnic University of Timișoara	Romania	Y
(UR) University of Reunion Island	France	
(USV) Ștefan cel Mare University of Suceava	Romania	Y
(USZ) University of Szeged	Hungary	Y
(UT) Université de Tours	France	
(UT) University of Tübingen	Germany	
(UT1) Toulouse 1 Capitole University	France	
(UU) Utrecht University	Netherlands	
(UvA) University of Amsterdam	Netherlands	
(UVT) West University of Timișoara	Romania	Y
(UZA) Universidad de Zaragoza	Spain	
(UZH) University of Zurich	Switzerland	
(ViA) Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences	Latvia	Y

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(VUB) Vrije Universiteit Brussel	Belgium	
(VY) University of Vaasa	Finland	
(WROCLAW TECH) Wrocław University of Science and Technology	Poland	Y
(Západočeská univerzita v Plzni (UWB)) University of West Bohemia	Czech Republic	Y
Cukurova University	Turkey	Y
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences	Hungary	Y
Leibniz University Hannover	Germany	
Örebro University	Sweden	
Palacký University Olomouc	Czech Republic	Y
Università degli Studi di Milano Statale	Italy	
University of Limoges	France	
University of Sussex	United Kingdom	

APPENDIX C

aUPaEU – Branding Guidelines and Identity Elements

This document outlines the visual identity of aUPaEU, including its branding design and usage guidelines.

Branding Guidelines for aUPaEU

Brand identity elements

Our focus is the integration and implementation of acceleration services for the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions. By developing a digital platform, Agora, we provide tangible acceleration services towards HEIs transformation.

MISSION

aUPaEU's mission is to provide digital services to accelerate the transformation of Higher Education Institutions. We focus on six major areas of the HEI transformation agenda: capacity, infrastructure, and resource sharing; researcher career attractiveness; collaboration with R&I ecosystem actors; open science; societal outreach; and gender equality.

VISION

The vision of aUPaEU is to enable integrated, shared, and long-term research and innovation transformations across European universities. By fostering collaborative environments reminiscent of the ancient Greek agora, the initiative aims to create ecosystems where creativity and innovation can flourish, thereby strengthening Europe's global competitiveness in higher education and research.

Empower Universities
Accelerate Transformation
Step into Agora

Logo

01

Concept

The aUPaEU logo visually represents the essence of the initiative: collaboration, diversity, and the collective advancement of European universities. At the core of the design is a flower-shaped emblem composed of multiple colorful petals, each symbolizing a different partner university. The unity of these petals reflects the synergy and cooperation between institutions, working together to strengthen the European Higher Education landscape.

Brand isotype, isologo & imagotype

The center of the flower, in a bright yellow shade, symbolizes knowledge, growth, and excellence—the shared goals of all participating institutions. It acts as the focal point, uniting the different contributions of each partner into a common purpose.

The flower represents unity, inclusivity, and the interconnected nature of the universities within aUPaEU. It reflects the idea that higher education institutions are stronger when they collaborate, share resources, and support each other.

Each petal has a distinct color, emphasizing the diversity of universities, cultures, and academic strengths within the initiative.

The variety of colors also represents innovation, transformation, and the dynamic nature of education in Europe.

By combining these elements, the aUPaEU logo encapsulates the project's mission: to empower universities, foster collaboration, and elevate educational excellence across Europe. It is a bold and vibrant visual identity that aligns with the initiative's values and long-term vision.

Isotype on three diferent backgrounds

Imagotype on three diferent backgrounds

isologo on three diferent backgrounds

Proper and Improper Logo Usage

Logo Structure and Proportions

Free space

To preserve the strength and integrity of the logo, it is essential to maintain a clear space around it, free from any visual elements that may compete with it or create visual clutter.

Ensuring Proper Logo Coexistence

EXAMPLE 01

EXAMPLE 02

When used alongside other logos, our logo must maintain its integrity, visibility, and hierarchy. Proper spacing and alignment should be observed to ensure balance and avoid visual clutter. In co-branding scenarios, all logos should be presented in a way that respects their individual identities while maintaining a cohesive visual relationship. The logo should never be altered, resized disproportionately, or placed too close to competing elements. Clear space guidelines must always be followed to uphold brand consistency and recognition.

Colour

02

aUPaEU
GRADIENT COLOUR

- HEX #FB5607
- HEX #FF006E
- HEX #8338EC
- HEX #3A86FF
- HEX #FFB6D9

Deep Violet

HEX #8338EC

RGB 131 56 236

CMYK 74,8% 78,45% 0% 0%

Vibrant Orange

HEX #FB5607

RGB 251 86 7

CMYK 0% 80,73% 100% 0%

Lavander Mist

HEX #F2E9F6

RGB 242 229 246

CMYK 5,65% 7,11% 0,56% 0%

Midnight Navy

HEX #001E4D

RGB 0 30 77

CMYK 99,37% 86,43% 39,75% 43,43%

VIBRANT ORANGE

Dark	#F05105	100%
Light	#FB5607	100%
		75%
		65%
		55%
		45%
		25%
		10%

ELECTRIC PINK

Dark	#F00068	100%
Light	#FF006E	100%
		75%
		65%
		55%
		45%
		25%
		10%

DEEP VIOLET

Dark	#7A2AEB	100%
Light	#8338EC	100%
		75%
		65%
		55%
		45%
		25%
		10%

CRISP BLUE

Dark	#2E7AF2	100%
Light	#3A86FF	100%
		75%
		65%
		55%
		45%
		25%
		10%

GOLDEN YELLOW

Dark	#6B5000	100%
Light	#FFB6D9	100%
		75%
		65%
		55%
		45%
		25%
		10%

#8338EC
Accent colour

#FA5607
Orange colour

#001E4D
Tint colour

aUPaEU colour gradient

Pure White colour

Crisp White colour

Lavender Mist colour

Dark Navy colour

Roboto

Aa

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

1234567890 !@#\$%&'()*=?

Å € ' @ + ¥ " " ^ ø π " ' << ä ß ð f © ·

Roboto has a dual nature. It has a mechanical skeleton and the forms are largely geometric. At the same time, the font features friendly and open curves. While some grotesks distort their letterforms to force a rigid rhythm, Roboto doesn't compromise, allowing letters to be settled into their natural width. This makes for a more natural reading rhythm more commonly found in humanist and serif types.

Updated July 2020: Upgraded to a variable font with Weight and Width axes, that closely match the previous static fonts released as two families, this one and a sibling Roboto Condensed family.

Roboto is part of a superfamily set that includes Roboto Slab and Roboto Mono.

Typeface sizes
The image showcases the different font weights and sizes available for Roboto. Each row represents a different weight and the columns list the different test sizes.

Light 112

- Headline 1
- Headline 2
- Headline 3
- Headline 4
- Headline 5
- Title
- Subheading
- Body 2
- Body 1
- Caption
- Button

Regular 56

Regular 45

Regular 34

Regular 24

Medium 20

Regular 16 (Device), Regular 15 (Desktop)

Medium 14 (Device), Medium 13 (Desktop)

Regular 14 (Device), Regular 13 (Desktop)

Regular 12sp

MEDIUM (ALL CAPS) 14sp

"We see Roboto as an evolving type family and that is central to our design and update strategy. It's important to us that a type family stays relevant and usable, even without change for many years. Sometimes an updated version is released with a new name, sometimes by appending a 'New' or 'Next'. The old model for releasing fonts as patches doesn't make sense for an operating system that is constantly improving. As the system evolves over time, the type should evolve along with it." - Google

Type Pairing

01
Aa

Examples of typography in use

USAGE

Headline, Body, Numeric, UI

MEDIUM 25

March 10, 2025

MEDIUM 180

+25%

LIGHT 30

OpEx comparison n°1

REGULAR 80

The Importance of
Typefaces

REGULAR 25

How to implement the typeface to our designs

MEDIUM 18

Read more →

Examples of typography in use

aUPaEU
FIRST DL

PROFESSOR MATHIEU LAFONT
aUPaEU
PROFESSOR MATHIEU LAFONT
aUPaEU
PROFESSOR MATHIEU LAFONT
aUPaEU

ID
CARD

NAME: MATHIEU LAFONT
ID: 123456789
EXPIRES: 31/12/2025

Opening Agora to Companies
Benefits and challenges
for HEI Alliances

THE CHALLENGE OF OPENING AGORA TO COMPANIES IS TO FIND A BALANCE BETWEEN THE NEEDS OF HEI ALLIANCES AND THE NEEDS OF COMPANIES. THIS IS A CHALLENGE THAT REQUIRES A STRATEGIC APPROACH AND A COLLABORATIVE EFFORT.

Facilitating Innovation

Bridging the gap between business and academia to foster innovation

How collaboration between academia and industry, supported by acceleration services, drives research, development, and institutional transformation in higher education.

The innovation landscape has fundamentally changed in the last decade. The pace of technological change is accelerating, and the gap between business and academia is widening. This is a challenge that requires a strategic approach and a collaborative effort.

Stationary

05

To better visualize the application of our brand identity, the following section presents various mockups showcasing its implementation across different formats and channels. These examples will help illustrate how our colors, typography, and design elements come together to create a cohesive and impactful brand presence in both digital and physical environments.

